

GRAY AND CRUICKSHANK'S METHOD AND THE DIAMAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITIES OF DICYANDIAMIDE, ACETAMIDE AND CYANURIC ACID

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Magnetic susceptibilities of dicyandiamide, acetamide, and cyanuric acid have been measured on very carefully purified specimens. The values found have been compared with those calculated by Gray and Cruickshank's method, using the resonating structures established by X-ray analysis of their crystals. A survey of the results indicates that though the values given by Gray and Cruickshank's method of calculation prove to be a decided improvement upon those derived from Pascal's procedure, still the agreement between the experimental and calculated values is not sufficiently close in all cases. In the case of cyanuric acid there is a large difference between the two values for every possible single or resonating structure of the molecule.

Pascal's pioneer work, based on magnetic measurement, has made a notable contribution towards the analysis of molecular structure of organic compounds, except in certain cases of substances containing both nitrogen and oxygen. Gray and Cruickshank (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, **31**, 1491) have developed a new method for the magnetic analysis of both resonating and non-resonating molecular structures. Their method of calculation is based on the following factors :—

(a) Ionic diamagnetisms, calculated on the basis of a modification of Pauling's formula (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1927, **114A**, 181).

(b) Residual charges, due to unequal sharing of bond electrons, calculated from the dipole moments of the bonds.

(c) Bond depression of diamagnetism, which, according to these authors, is partly, to a small extent, real lowering of pure diamagnetism, but mainly masking (without lowering) of pure diamagnetism by the development of high frequency paramagnetism, as indicated by quantum mechanical calculations for the simple molecule of hydrogen.

(d) Resonance between possible structures for the molecule, each resonating form contributing its due share to the diamagnetism of the resultant molecule.

(e) Formation of H-bond where hydrogen-bridges are possible.

A detailed discussion of this method of calculation will be found in their paper (*loc. cit.*).

The present work was undertaken with a view to testing the validity of this method in the case of some simple organic molecules containing nitrogen, for which the Pascal's method usually fails. The compounds selected are dicyandiamide, acetamide and cyanuric acid, the details of whose structures are definitely known from X-ray measurements. The susceptibilities of these compounds, calculated on the basis of Gray and Cruickshank's method, were compared with those experimentally observed. The results, however, did not furnish a consistent and satisfactory agreement. The various values required for calculating susceptibilities were taken from Gray and Cruickshank's paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Compounds

Dicyandiamide.—Extra pure dicyandiamide (Merck) was recrystallised five times from water and the susceptibilities of the fourth and the fifth fractions were measured.

Acetamide.—Merck's extra pure acetamide was distilled twice in vacuum and the purest middle fractions of the first and the second distillate were used. (B.P. 99° at 7 mm. pressure).

Cyanuric Acid.—This was prepared by heating urea with anhydrous ZnCl₂ at 190-200° in an oil-bath until all ammonia was expelled. The product was washed from all soluble matters with hot water and repeatedly crystallised from conc. HCl (Fe-free). This was finally dried over KOH. The third and fourth fractions were used for susceptibility measurements. {Found (3rd crop) : N, 32.58. C₃H₃N₃O₃ requires N, 32.56 per cent}.

Measurements

The susceptibilities were measured according to Guoy's method. The field strength employed was 10.4×10^3 gauss with a current of 5 amperes. This was determined from a measurement on air-free conductivity water in the same tube in which other measurements were carried out; the value was corrected for air. The close agreement between values for two consecutive fractions of crystallisation or distillation product was taken as the criterion of purity of the substances concerned. All the measured values were corrected for air. The details of the magnetic balance and the method of measurement have been described in a previous paper from this laboratory (Ray and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 323).

The results of measurement are expected to be correct within 2 per cent.

The mass susceptibilities were calculated according to the formula :—

$$\chi_g = \frac{2 \times l \times m'}{m \times H^2 \times 1.019} + \chi_v^a / d_s$$

where χ_g is the gram susceptibility of the substance, χ_v^a is the volume susceptibility of air at t° , the temperature of measurement, l = the length of the tube in cm., m' = the change of weight in mg., m = the weight of the substance in g., H = the maximum field strength, and d_s = the density of the substance.

All susceptibility values given below are to be multiplied by 10^{-4} . The results of measurement are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Substance.	m .	l .	m' .	χ_g un-corrected.	d_s .	t° .	χ_v^a .	χ_g corrected.	χ_m .
1. Dicyandiamide.									
(a) 4th frac.	3.404 g.	11.4 cm.	-9.05 mg.	-0.5501	1.404	29°	0.0276	-0.5304	-44.55
(b) 5th frac.	3.438	"	-9.14	-0.5500	"	"	"	"	"
2. Acetamide.									
(a) 1st dist.	4.446	11.4	-11.94	-0.5558	1.159	30°	0.0275	-0.5321	-31.39
(b) 2nd dist.	4.356	"	-11.74	-0.5577	"	"	"	-0.5340	-31.52
3. Cyanuric acid.									
(a) 3rd frac.	3.173	11.4	-7.54	-0.4917	1.72	31°	0.0273	-0.4758	-61.39
(b) 4th fract.	3.174	"	-7.58	-0.4939	"	"	"	-0.4780	-61.67

The density of cyanuric acid was determined at 30° with xylene as the filling liquid. Densities of other substances were taken from standard tables,

CALCULATED RESULTS

Dicyandiamide.—It has been shown by X-ray analysis that the substance resonates between the structures IA, IB and II. IA and IB contribute 75% in equal amounts and II contributes 25% to the normal state of the molecule (Hughes, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 1258).

According to Gray and Cruickshank's method of calculation we may consider IA and IB to be identical as their molecular susceptibilities will be equal. If again each double bond is split up into a polarised single co-valent bond, as suggested by Gray and Cruickshank, then I and II will assume in addition the equivalent structures III and IV respectively.

Under these circumstances the resultant molecular susceptibility of the compound would be $3/8$ due to I, $3/8$ due to III, $1/8$ due to II and $1/8$ due to IV. Let us denote this as case A.

If, however, the triple bond is also supposed to split up like the double bond, then the structure II will likewise lead to an alternative configuration identical with III. The resultant molecular susceptibility under this condition will be made up of $3/8$ due to I, $1/8$ due to II and the rest $1/2$ due to III (case A').

If, however, we ignore III and IV, the resultant molecular susceptibility will be $3/4$ due to I and $1/4$ due to II (case B).

Till now we have not considered the H-bonds which play a very important part in building up the crystal lattice. The disposition of H-bonds as found from X-ray analysis is denoted by V.

The direction of the arrows indicates the N-atoms which accept the H-atoms forming the H-bonds. There is a bifurcated H-bond between N_{II} atom of each molecule and two adjacent N_{IV} atoms of two different molecules.

On consideration of the effect of these H-bonds Gray and Cruickshank's method of calculation gives a new value for the resultant molecular susceptibility for each of the structures I, II, III and IV, and consequently in each of the cases A, A' and B discussed above. Table II summarises the results of calculation.

TABLE II

Structure.	Experimental value = 44.55			Resonance contribution.
	χ_M (G & C. without H-bonds).	χ_M (G & C. with H-bonds).	χ_M Pascal.	
I	31.65	25.39	22.4	
II	38.41	40.73 ^a	37.0	
III	58.45	59.41		
IV	45.66	45.49 ^b		
Case A	44.30	43.98		$3/8(\text{I}) + 3/8(\text{II}) + 1/8(\text{III}) + 1/8(\text{IV})$
„ A'	45.90	44.32		$3/8(\text{I}) + 1/8(\text{II}) + 1/2(\text{III})$
„ B	31.84	29.23	26.1	$3/4(\text{I}) + 1/4(\text{II})$

* In calculating these two values it was necessary to assume the absence of bifurcated H-bonds between N_{II} and N_{IV} atoms, since the N_{IV} atom, having only one lone pair of electrons, can receive only one H-bond from outside. In fact, the X-ray analysis also shows that the interatomic distance between N_{II} and N_{IV} atoms is somewhat larger than the N—N distance with a H-bond between them.

In the above calculations the bond depressions for C—N and N—H bonds have been taken to be equal to those of C—O and O—H-bonds respectively. This is not likely to affect the resultant susceptibility as the values are very small, and particularly since the oxygen and nitrogen atoms are closely similar in respect of weight and electronegativity.

It appears that the resonating structure of case A with or without H-bonds as well as that of A' with hydrogen bonds give values agreeing closely with experimental results.

2. *Acetamide*.—The acetamide molecule has been found to resonate equally between the structures VI and VII from X-ray analysis of its crystal (Senti and Harker, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 2008).

The polarised single bond structure VIII will arise in both cases if the double bond is split up as assumed by Gray and Cruickshank.

Structure IX shows the distribution of hydrogen bonds in the crystal lattice as found by X-ray analysis. Each H-atom of NH_2 -group is linked to two oxygen atoms in different adjacent molecules in every structure.

Considering the splitting up of double bonds the resultant molecular susceptibility will be made up of $1/4$ due to VI, $1/4$ due to VII and $1/2$ due to VIII (case A). Otherwise it would arise out of $1/2$ the contribution from VI and $1/2$ from VII (case B). The values are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Structure.	χ_m (G & C without H-bonds).	χ_m (G & C with H-bonds).	χ_m (f'ascal).	Resonance contribution.
VI	31'70	33'43	26'39	
VII	28'73	30'96	24'55	
VIII	40'14	42'36		
Case A	34'93	37'30		1/4(VI)+ 1/4(VII)+ 1/2(VIII).
Case B	29'72	32'20	25'47	1/2(VI)+ 1/2(VII).

Experimental value = 31'39, 31'52.

TABLE IV

Structure.	χ_m (G & C without H-bonds).	χ_m (G & C with H-bonds).	χ_m f'ascal.	Resonance contribution.
X	39'26	43'03	35'15	
XI	38'89	37'23		
XII	67'73	72'04		
Case A	51'71	55'59		1/6(X)+ 1/3(XI)+ 1/2(XII).
Case B	35'69	39'14		1/3(X)+ 2/3(XI).

Experimental value = 61'39, 61'67.

For Gray and Cruickshank's method the nearest approach to the experimental value is found in case B with or without H-bonds, which does not consider the splitting up of double bonds.

3. *Cyanuric Acid*.—The molecule has been found by X-ray analysis to resonate equally among the structures X, XIA and XIB (Wiebenga and Moerman, *Z. Krist.*, 1938, 99, 217).

The molar susceptibility, calculated according to Gray and Cruickshank's method will give

X

XIA

XIB

identical values for XI A and XI B, and each of the structures X, XIA and XIB will assume the configuration XII if the double bonds are split up. Structure XIII shows the distribution of H-bonds in the crystal lattice.

XII

XIII

Considering the splitting up of double bonds the resultant molecular susceptibility, calculated according to Gray and Cruickshank's method, would be 1/6 due to X, 1/3 due to XI (A + B) and 1/2 due to XII (case A). Otherwise, it will be made up of 1/3 due to X and 2/3 due to XI (case B). The values are shown in Table IV.

The experimental value does not agree with any of the calculated ones.

DISCUSSION

A survey of the results obtained in the cases examined shows a decided improvement in the susceptibility values, when calculated according to Gray and Cruickshank's method, over those given by Pascal's procedure. Still, the agreement with experimental values is not in every case close enough to justify its adoption. Besides, where there seems to be a close agreement, e.g., in the case of dicyandiamide (case A, with or without H-bonds, and case A' with H-bond; as well as in case B of acetamide with hydrogen bond, the anomaly remains that in the former the calculation is based on the splitting of double bonds into polarised single bonds, while in the latter it is ignored. In the case of cyanuric acid, however, the method fails altogether.

Remarkable agreements between experimental values and those calculated on the basis of Gray and Cruickshank's method reported by Clow and co-workers (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1937, 33, 381, 894; 1940, 36, 1018) in the cases of urea with its derivatives, organic sulphur compounds and derivatives of SO_4^- , S_2O_5^- , etc., are open to criticism, as consideration for hydrogen bonds and all types of resonance with their percentage contributions has not been made. In the case of urea, for instance, the two resonating structures, on the basis of Werner's formula, cannot contribute equally to the normal state of the molecule, since the structure resulting from the splitting of double bond must be comparatively much less stable, due to its having a smaller number of co-valent bonds and to the juxtaposition of positive charges.

It might be pointed out in this connection that the splitting of double bond in every case, as suggested by Gray and Cruickshank, has little theoretical justification behind it. The interatomic distance on this view cannot be made to agree with the observed values without some further *ad hoc* assumption.

Unless the method is further refined, it cannot be viewed upon as a reliable means for exploring the structure of molecules.

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